

CONSEQUENCES OF INCORRECT APPLICATION AND INTERPRETATION OF THE INTERNATIONAL TRADE RULES OF INCOTERMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14214304>

Annotation. The article reveals the main consequences associated with the incorrect application and interpretation of international trade rules INCOTERMS. On the part of the author to avoid disputes and misunderstandings at the conclusion of foreign economic transactions, the parties have developed recommendations related to the correct application of INCOTERMS.

Keywords: INCOTERMS, foreign economic transactions, international sale contract, interpretation, international trade rules, basis of delivery terms.

With the dynamic development of international trade relations, the contract for the sale of goods is one of the key legal and economic instruments. This type of contract regulates the terms of transfer of goods between the seller and the buyer, acting as a basis for trade facilitation at both global and national levels. In today's environment, such contracts not only promote economic integration, but also protect the interests of the parties.

INCOTERMS rules are designed to settle legal issues that are not reflected in the UN Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods 1980 and are not always equally understood in different countries.

At the same time, the correct use of INCOTERMS terms in foreign economic transactions, which determine the basic principles of distribution of responsibility, risks and costs between the parties, is of particular importance. Reflection in international contracts for the sale and purchase of goods INCOTERMS (indicating the wording of the Rules and the trade term) becomes a necessary element of successful conclusion of transactions. This makes it possible to avoid misunderstandings related to the interpretation of delivery terms and minimize risks arising in the performance of contractual obligations. However, incorrect application and interpretation of INCOTERMS may lead to significant consequences for the parties to the contract, including legal disputes, financial losses and disruption of business relations.

With the development of foreign economic and foreign trade relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan it is important to conclude foreign economic transactions only in the form of a contract for the international sale of goods and apply international trade rules INCOTERMS. In other types of foreign economic transactions, INCOTERMS rules are not applied, and only on the basis of the international contract of sale of goods, based on the trade term chosen by the parties, contracts of carriage and insurance are concluded.

A reference to INCOTERMS in a contract does not mean that their provisions will prevail over the express terms of the contract in interpreting the contract. In order to avoid disputes, it is advisable to “expressly provide in the contract that in interpreting the base terms, the provisions of INCOTERMS shall apply to the extent not otherwise specified in the contract”.

The use of INCOTERMS occurs in two cases: firstly, when it is necessary to refer to a specific trade term to determine the resolution of a dispute between the parties to an international sale of goods contract; secondly, when such direct reference is not required, but INCOTERMS is taken into account to assess the fulfilment of a party's duty. The use of universal trade terms allows largely preventing disputes and conflict situations at the stage of contract execution, the resolution of which requires various costs, as well as introduces elements of uncertainty into the relations of the parties.

Practice shows that the correct interpretation and precise application of INCOTERMS rules, as well as the basic terms of supply stipulated by these rules, play a key role in the development of foreign economic and trade relations between countries. However, at the stage of contract conclusion the parties often pay more attention to the financial side of the transaction than to a detailed analysis of the contractual terms and conditions. This attitude often leads to difficulties in the fulfilment of obligations, which, in turn, may cause conflicts and disputes.

Often the parties concluding a foreign trade contract are unfamiliar with different trade practices in the respective countries, which also leads to disputes. Therefore, the parties should carefully study the terms of the contract and the rules governing contractual relations, and especially pay attention to the terms used in the contract, i.e. when concluding contracts it is necessary to correctly use the basic terms of delivery, specifically refer to the version of the Rules applied in the contract, correctly interpret the applicable terms of INCOTERMS.

As DiMatteo correctly pointed out, when choosing trade terms, the parties should be aware of the possibility of conflicts between the chosen term and other terms of the contract. For example, the CIF term shifts the risk for the goods to the buyer at the port of shipment. If the contract provides that the seller guarantees a certain quantity and quality of the goods upon their arrival at the place of destination, there is an obvious conflict between this term and the trade term, since the risk for the goods is again transferred to the buyer. The question arises - which term will determine the liability for the goods in transit in this case? The tendency of the American courts is inclined to favour the CIF term. One may agree with its contention that a deviation from the trade term should not destroy the essence or the whole meaning of the term, which is a contract of dispatch but not of delivery.

When concluding a foreign economic contract, it is necessary to clearly define the details of the basic delivery term. As practice shows, a mere reference to the relevant INCOTERMS term is not enough, since the INCOTERMS provisions are general in many matters, offering only a principled solution.

Despite the complete clarity and transparency of the provisions of INCOTERMS terms, in practice it is not uncommon for legal conflicts to arise regarding the correct interpretation and application of a particular term. It happens that the parties to a foreign economic contract do not pay attention to the fact that the Rules regulate relations only between the seller and the buyer and do not concern the relations of counterparties with carriers, forwarders and other persons who may take part in a foreign economic transaction. Therefore, in some contracts, in addition to referring to the Rules, the parties try to include in a specific term provisions concerning the carriage of goods and responsibility for its proper performance. Such provisions in relation to the Rules are incorrect and should be stated, although in accordance with them, but not as established by them. It is also quite common that the parties to a contract 'forget' to specify which version of the Rules they have in mind. This shortcoming is of significant importance in court proceedings because of the difference between the 2010 and 2020 editions of the Rules.

When considering disputes over the application of INCOTERMS, courts are often faced with the question of which version of the rules should be used. One approach involves analyzing the parties' previous practice in using these rules and considering the content of a particular term in the context of the entire contract. Courts avoid automatically applying the latest version of INCOTERMS, thereby preserving the parties' freedom to set terms within their ordinary legal

relationship. This approach also helps the court to gain a deeper understanding of the agreements.

The Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Certain Issues of Application of Legislative Acts in the Consideration by Economic Courts of Cases Involving Foreign Persons', which provides that an economic court in resolving a dispute may apply international business practices, including the International Rules for the Interpretation of Trade Terms (Incoterms) and the Principles of International Commercial Contracts (Unidroit), in cases where they do not contradict the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the parties expressly stated so in the contract.

The correct application and interpretation of INCOTERMS simplifies the structure of a contract for the international sale of goods by eliminating excessive detail of obligations. This is achieved through standardized provisions on the rights and obligations of the parties, which are already embedded in specific trade terms.

In order to avoid disputes and misunderstandings when concluding foreign economic transaction, the parties are advised to take into account the following aspects related to the application of INCOTERMS:

1. Precise indication of the terms of delivery: When selecting the basis of delivery, INCOTERMS terminology should be used, preferably in English. It is also important to indicate the specific place (geographical location) where the seller is deemed to have fulfilled his obligations.
2. Specifying the INCOTERMS version: The contract should clearly state which version applies (e.g. INCOTERMS 2020). This eliminates the risk of confusion and facilitates the application of the terms.
3. Conformity with the terms of delivery: The use of inappropriate terms or their application in inappropriate situations can lead to disputes. Terms should be transaction-specific and clearly reflect the allocation of risks and costs.
4. Specification of the basis of delivery: The terms of delivery in the contract should be supplemented by specific provisions specifying the allocation of responsibilities and risks between the parties to avoid uncertainties.
5. Optimizing the choice of term: The choice of the appropriate term should take into account the actual delivery mechanism in order to minimize risks and costs. For example, in containerized transport, FCA, CPT or CIP are most often preferred over CFR or CIF.
6. Explicit reference to INCOTERMS: INCOTERMS delivery bases are only valid when explicitly referenced in the contract. If the legislation of the

counterparty's country makes INCOTERMS binding, this must be taken into account.

7. Contradictions in the terms of the contract: If the terms of the contract contradict the INCOTERMS provisions, the contractual provisions shall prevail.

8. Comprehensive approach to price: The indication of the price of the goods, taking into account the basis of delivery, must be carefully considered to be in the interests of the parties and market realities.

The consequences of non-compliance with these requirements include inability to fulfil obligations, conflicts, and additional costs and time lost in resolving disputes. Correct application of INCOTERMS reduces risks and facilitates the realization of foreign economic transactions.

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